

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning

Machine learning is an application of artificial intelligence (AI) that provides systems the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning focuses on the development of computer programs that can access data and use it learn for themselves. The process of learning begins with observations or data, such as examples, direct experience, or instruction, in order to look for patterns in data and make better decisions in the future based on the examples that we provide. The primary aim is to allow the computers learn automatically without human intervention or assistance and adjust actions accordingly.

Machine Learning Methods

Machine learning algorithms are often categorized as supervised or unsupervised.

Supervised machine learning algorithms can apply what has been learned in the past to new data using labeled examples to predict future events. Starting from the analysis of a known training dataset, the learning algorithm produces an inferred function to make predictions about the output values. The system is able to provide targets for any new input after sufficient training. The learning algorithm can also compare its output with the correct, intended output and find errors in order to modify the model accordingly.

In contrast, **unsupervised machine learning algorithms** are used when the information used to train is neither classified nor labeled. Unsupervised learning studies how systems can infer a function to describe a hidden structure from unlabeled data. The system doesn't figure out the right output, but it explores the data and can draw inferences from datasets to describe hidden structures from unlabeled data.

Reinforcement machine learning algorithms is a learning method that interacts with its environment by producing actions and discovers errors or rewards. Trial and error search and delayed reward are the most relevant characteristics of reinforcement learning. This method allows machines and software agents to automatically determine the ideal behavior within a specific context in order to maximize its performance. Simple reward feedback is required for the agent to learn which action is best; this is known as the reinforcement signal.

Advantages of Machine Learning

- ✓ Machine Learning undoubtedly helps people to work more creatively and efficiently.
- ✓ Machine learning algorithms are capable of learning from data we provide.
- ✓ It identifies various trends and patterns with huge amount of data.
- ✓ It is used in wide range of application.
- ✓ A very powerful utility of machine learning is its ability to automate various decision-making tasks.

1.2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

There are generally two approaches for hand gesture recognition, which are hardware based, where the user must wear a device, and the other is vision based which uses Machine learning techniques with inputs from a camera. The proposed system is vision based, which uses machine learning techniques and inputs from a computer webcam. Vision based gesture recognition tracking and gesture recognition. The input frame would be captured from the webcam and systems are generally broken down into four stages, skin detection, hand contour extraction, hand the skin region would be detected using skin detection.

The hand contour would then be found and used for hand tracking and gesture recognition. Hand tracking would be used to navigate the computer cursor and hand gestures would be used to perform mouse functions such as right click, left click, scroll up and scroll down. The scope of the project would therefore be to design a vision-based CC system, which

can perform the mouse function previously stated.

In short, the Flowchart for our project will be as follows:

1.3 PROJECT DEFINITION:

The first challenge was to correctly detect the hand with a webcam. We needed a Computer Vision library for this purpose. Many are available but we decided to go ahead with OpenCV as it is the most popular and has been ported to many languages and is supported on many operating systems from Android to Windows. It has a good library collection of standard image processing functions. Then we had to first setup OpenCV on our IDE(ANACONDA NAVIGATOR). That was a very tedious task. We also had to learn some basic usage of OpenCV. For which we referred to many tutorials on the web. After learning OpenCV, We had to learn about the skin detection techniques and image processing techniques like Background Subtraction, Image Smoothing, Noise Removal and Reduction.

Now, after detecting the hand correctly and mapping the gestures, we had to learn to use the Windows API in order tune the software with the Metro UI. For learning it, we built some basic applications based on it. So, in short, there was a steep learning curve. As, high-end cameras and sensors are very costly we decided to go with a simple webcam. So, we decided to optimize our software and its functionality in order the drawback of using a simple webcam. Also, for testing our project we had a primary requirement of having a white background with no visible part except our palm.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

PAPER 1: “Glove-based hand gesture recognition sign language translator using capacitive touch sensor”

Authors: K.S. Abhishek, L.C.F. Qubeley, D. Ho

Year: 2018

Description:

We present an intelligent electronic glove system able to detect numbers of sign language in order to automate the process of communication between a deaf-mute person and others. This is done by translating the hands move sign language into an oral language. The system is inside to a glove with flex sensors in each finger that we are used to collect data that are analyzed through a methodology involving the following stages: Data balancing with the Kennard-Stone, comparison of prototypes algorithm and Incremental Reduction Optimization Procedure (DROIP) to define the best one, the K-Nearest Neighbors as classifier is implemented. The sign language translator is a bridge between those who comprehend sign languages and those who do not which is the majority of humanity. However, conventional sign language translators are bulky and expensive, limiting their wide adoption. In this paper, we present a gesture recognition glove based on charge-transfer touch sensors for the translation of the American Sign Language. The device is portable and can be implemented with low-cost hardware. The prototype recognize gestures for the numbers 0 to 9 and the 26 English alphabets, A to Z. The glove experimentally achieved, based on 1080 trials, an overall detection accuracies of over 92 %, which is comparable with current high-end counterparts. The proposed device is expected to bridge the communication gap between the hearing and speech impaired and members of the general public.

PAPER 2: “Using AEPI method for hand gesture recognition in varying background and blurred images”

Authors: A.V. Dehankar ; Sanjeev Jain ; V. M. Thakare

Year: 2017

Description:

Due to the advancement in technology, new methods for human computer interaction are getting developed very rapidly. Interacting with computers or mobile devices through hand gestures is one of the important research areas where researchers are trying to implement new user interfaces by applying various methods. In this paper, the Accurate End Point Identification method is implemented and applied on gesture images which are captured in varying background and it is also applied on blurred images containing multiple objects. The AEPI method accurately recognizes the gestures from such images and provides a new dimension to implement user interface that will help to provide more natural inputs through hand gestures. In such situation time and accuracy are two important factors to recognize the Hand Gesture in 3D-Space. So, in this paper we propose a new method called Hand Gesture Recognition Using Accurate End Point Identification (AEPI) method. This method not only recognizes Hand Gesture in less time only but also with high percentage of accuracy. Our proposed work is compared with the current working system to measure the accuracy of our system. Our system mainly focuses on the mobile computing and image processing using Morphological Computations. The accuracy of this system is 93%. Many systems are unable to identify the fingers which are connected to each other. This system is able to identify the fingers which are connected to each other.

PAPER 3 “Motion Fused Frames: Data Level Fusion Strategy for Hand Gesture Recognition”

Authors: O. Köpüklü, N. Köse, and G. Rigoll

Year: 2018

Description:

Acquiring spatio-temporal states of an action is the most crucial step for action classification. In this paper, we propose a data level fusion strategy, Motion Fused Frames (MFFs), designed to fuse motion information into static images as better representatives of spatio-temporal states of an action. MFFs can be used as input to any deep learning architecture with very little modification on the network. We evaluate MFFs on hand gesture recognition tasks using three video datasets - Jester, ChaLearn LAP IsoGD and NVIDIA Dynamic Hand Gesture Datasets - which require capturing long-term temporal relations of hand movements. Our approach obtains very competitive performance on Jester and ChaLearn benchmarks with the classification accuracies of 96.28% and 57.4%, respectively, while achieving state-of-the-art performance with 84.7% accuracy on NVIDIA benchmark. The temporal information in videos has been analyzed using different modalities such as RGB, depth, infrared and flow images as input. The results show that although each of these modalities provide good recognition performances alone, the fusion analysis of these modalities further increases the recognition performance.

PAPER 4: “Real-time hand gesture recognition with EMG using machine learning”

Authors: Andrés G. Jaramillo ; Marco E. Benalcázar, 2017

Year:2017

Description:

In this paper, we propose the development of a model for real-time hand gesture recognition. We use surface electromyography (EMG) and Machine Learning techniques. The recognition of gestures using EMG is not a trivial task because there are several physiological processes in the skeletal muscles underlying their generation. In the scientific literature, there are several hand gesture recognition models, but they have limitations both in the number of gestures to be recognized (i.e., classes) and in the processing time. Therefore, the primary goal of this research is to obtain a real-time hand gesture recognition model for various applications in the field of medicine and engineering with a higher recognition accuracy than the real-time models proposed in the scientific literature and a higher number of gestures to recognize (i.e. in the order of the dozens). The proposed model has five stages: acquisition of the EMG signals, preprocessing (e.g., rectification and filtering), feature extraction (e.g., time, frequency and time-frequency), classification (e.g., parametric and nonparametric) and post-processing. Generally, the main difficulties of the hand gesture recognition models with EMG using Machine Learning are: the noisy behavior of EMG signal, and the small number of gestures per person relative to the number of generated data by each gesture (e.i., curse of dimensionality). Solving these two issues could also lead to solutions for other problems such as face recognition and audio recognition, for which these two issues are a major concern.

PAPER 5: “Comparative study for vision based and databased hand gesture recognition technique”

Authors: Oinam Robita Chanu, Anushree Pillai, Spandan Sinha and Priyanka Das

Year: 2017

Description:

Communication for mute people has always been very difficult. Mute people use hand gestures, also known as sign language to communicate with normal people. Hand gestures have their assigned meanings which may differ from person to person and hence cannot be understood by normal people. To overcome this difficulty many vision-based hand gesture recognition systems and data glove based hand gesture recognition systems have been proposed. This paper illustrates about two different techniques of vision-based hand gesture recognition and one data glove based technique. The vision - based techniques are static hand gesture recognition technique and real-time hand gesture recognition technique. In both the techniques, MATLAB software is used for processing input images and no dataset is used for decision making which makes this system more accurate than the existing system designs. In data glove based technique, the glove consists of five flex sensors. The change in resistance of flex sensor is used to recognize the hand gesture. All the three techniques are performed on 10 subjects and compared to find the most accurate technique. It was found that both the vision based techniques showed 100% accuracy in bright lighting condition with a white background while the data glove based technique showed an accuracy of 86%. This which clearly shows that mentioned vision based is more stable and reliable compared to the data glove based technique.

PAPER 6: “Performance analysis of RTEPI method for real time hand gesture recognition”

Authors: A.V. Dehankar ; Sanjeev Jain ; V. M. Thakare

Year:2017

Description:

Hand gestures provide a natural and intuitive way to interact with the computers, mobile devices, etc. Many researchers are working on gesture recognition where the aim is to identify and distinguish human gestures and then identified gestures are used to control applications in specific domains. Recognizing real time hand gestures is very challenging and difficult task. This paper presents a novel Real Time End Point Identification Method from a real time video of hand gesture using computer vision and Image processing techniques. The Real Time End Point Identification (RTEPI) method discussed in [1] is based on Accurate End Point Identification [2], which enables the AEPI method to work on real time hand gestures captured through web camera or laptop camera. The RTEPI method provides the correct frame for real time processing to AEPI method which then detects the accurate method. The AEPI method has been implemented to address the problems of varying background, luminance, blurring etc. Five different phases of AEPI method includes preprocessing, centroid detection, removal of unwanted objects, thinning and recognition which are already discussed in [2,3]. The paper presents the result and performance analysis of RTEPI method for all possible input patterns of real time hand gesture recognition.

PAPER 7: “Using AEPI method for hand gesture recognition in varying background and blurred images.”

Authors: A.V. Dehankar ; Sanjeev Jain ; V. M. Thakare, 2017

Year:2017

Description:

Due to the advancement in technology, new methods for human computer interaction are getting developed very rapidly. Interacting with computers or mobile devices through hand gestures is one of the important research area where researchers are trying to implement new user interfaces by applying various methods. The Hand Gesture Recognition system is useful to detect the gestures with the help of image capturing devices installed on computer and other gadgets. The rapid growth and improvement of mobile phones in past few years led to innovations in visualization and interaction with devices. Touchscreen gestures are widely used for interactivity in such devices but in near future the users may demand for more natural interaction methods. In this paper, the Accurate End Point Identification method is implemented and applied on gesture images which are captured in varying background and it is also applied on blurred images containing multiple objects. The AEPI method accurately recognizes the gestures from such images and provides a new dimension to implement user interface that will help to provide more natural inputs through hand gestures.

PAPER 8: “Detection and recognition of hand gesture for wearable applications in IoMTW”

Authors: Anna Yang ; Sung Moon Chun ; Jae-Gon Kim

Year: 2017

Description:

To support an efficient media consumption in a wearable device and IoT (Internet of Things) environment, the standardization of IoMTW (Internet of Media-Things and Wearables) is in the progress in MPEG (Moving Picture Experts Group). In this paper, we present a hand gesture detection and recognition algorithm to generate hand gesture-based commands for controlling the media consumption in smart glasses. In the proposed method, we use depth map and color image together to extract more accurate hand contour. We are going to present representation of the detected hand contour based on Bezier curve as metadata to provide an interoperable interface between a detection module and a recognition module. In a recognition module, the detected hand contour is reconstructed by parsing the delivered metadata. In the proposed recognition method, a set of hand gestures featured with diverse combination of open fingers and rotational angles can be recognized with quite stable performance in the proposed method. Finally, the recognized hand gesture is mapped into one of the pre-defined gesture commands.

PAPER 9: “Hand Gesture Recognition System for Touch-Less Car Interface Using Multiclass Support Vector Machine.”

Authors: Mrinalini Pramod Tarvekar

YEAR: 2018

Description:

Touch-less car interfaces are getting the attention in automobile industries. By using the hand gestures, it is possible to control some activities of cars, for this effective recognition system for hand gesture is required. This paper presents the recognition system of hand gesture for touch-less car interface. This system accepts video frames sequence and segmentation is applied on these frames. Here the new segmentation method is applied by detecting skin portion using HSV, YCgCr and YCbCr color space. From the segmented images their color and edge characteristics are extracted and then stored in the database with their respective labels. Edge histogram descriptor is used for retrieving the shape characteristics from images where a colour structure descriptor (CSD) is used to capture the spatial distribution of color in an image. Then for identification of gesture multiclass SVM classifier is used. For the experiment, hand gesture database from Cambridge is used where video-based frames of images are present for 9 gestures. Feature extraction is of the crucial task in the process as it helps to detect accurate hand gesture. Feature extraction is like a data reduction process which accepts the 2D image array as an input and gives feature vector output. Identifying which features has to select from image such that it will give the most descriptive information about the image such as edges, corners, ridges, blobs, etc is the important task. The mostly used feature extraction techniques are Template matching, Unitary Image transforms, Gabor features, Deformable templates, Graph description, Contour profiles, Zoning, Projection Histograms, Geometric moment invariants, Spline curve approximation, Fourier descriptors, Zernike Moments, and Gradient feature.

PAPER 10: “A New Dataset and Benchmark for Egocentric Hand Gesture Recognition.”

Authors: Y.Zhang,J.Cheng and H.Lu

Year:2018

Description:

Gesture is a natural interface in human computer interaction, especially interacting with wearable devices such as VR/AR helmet and glasses. However, in the gesture recognition community, it lacks of suitable datasets for developing egocentric (first-person) gesture recognition methods, in particular in the deep learning era. In this paper, we introduce a new benchmark dataset named EgoGesture with sufficient size, variation and reality, to be able to train deep neural networks. This dataset contains more than 24,000 gesture samples and 3,000,000 frames for both color and depth modalities from 50 distinct subjects. We design 83 different static or dynamic gestures focused on interaction with wearable devices and collect them from 6 diverse indoor and outdoor scenes respectively with variation in background and illumination. We also consider the scenario when people perform gestures while they are walking. The performances of several representative approaches are systematically evaluated on two tasks: gesture classification in segmented data and gesture spotting and recognition in continuous data. Our empirical study also provides an in-depth analysis on input modality selection and domain adaptation between different scenes

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In our existing system, a two-level hierarchical structure consisting of a detector and a classifier is proposed which enables offline working convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures to operate online efficiently by using sliding window approach. For efficiency analysis, different CNN architectures are applied to compare these architectures over offline classification accuracy.

The purpose of detector is to distinguish between gesture and no gesture classes by running on sequence of images, which detector queue masks. It is challenging mainly due to performed gestures should only be recognized once. The entire architecture should be designed considering memory and power. In order to evaluate the single-time activations of the detected gestures, the used levenshtein distance as an evaluation metric This is challenging mainly, there is no indication when gesture starts and ends and performed gesture should only be recognized once.

3.1.1 Drawbacks of Existing System

- ✓ Time consuming.
- ✓ CNN do not encode the position and orientation of object.
- ✓ It doesn't work so well with small data.
- ✓ Lack of ability to be spatially invariant to the input data.
- ✓ Low accuracy.
- ✓ The gesture can operate only in online.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this system, an anti-theft device which would be capable enough to detect theft using motion sensing camera using machine learning and alarm the owner with alert message along with the captured image of that instance of motion. Haar Cascade algorithm is used to train data. The device will be a real-time system along with easy to use interface, which will be proved useful in terms of security of people as well as their valuable things/objects.

Haar Cascade Algorithm

Haar Cascade is a machine learning object detection algorithm used to identify objects in an image or video.

The algorithm has four stages:

1. Haar Feature Selection
2. Creating Integral Images
3. Adaboost Training
4. Cascading Classifiers

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

1. To train more amount of data
2. High accuracy
3. Time consuming.
4. The gesture can operate in both online and offline.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the purpose and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is carried out. This ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential. Consequently benefits are estimated with greater accuracy at this stage. The key considerations are:

- Economic feasibility
- Technical feasibility
- Social feasibility

3.3.1 ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the development of the system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

3.3.3 SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

Fig 4.1 Architecture Diagram

4.2 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

➤ A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the “flow” of data through an information system, modeling its process aspects. Often, they are a preliminary step used to create an overview of the system which can later be elaborated. DFDs can also be used for the visualization of data processing.

0th Level:

Fig.4.2 Level 0 Dataflow Diagram

1st Level:

Fig 4.3 Level 1 Dataflow Diagram

2nd Level:

Fig 4.4 Level 2 Dataflow Diagram

4.3 UML DIAGRAMS

4.3.1 Use case Diagram

A use case diagram at its simplest is a representation of a user's interaction with the system and depicting the specification of a use case. A use case diagram can portray the different types of users of a system and the various ways that they interact with the system.

Fig 4.5 UML Diagram

4.3.2 Sequence Diagram:

A Sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how process operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart.

Fig 4.6 Sequence Diagram

4.3.3 Activity Diagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representation of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams are intended to a model both computational and organizational processes.

Fig 4.7 Activity Diagram

4.3.4 Class Diagram

The class diagram is the main building block of object-oriented modeling. It is used for general conceptual modeling of the structure of the application, and for detailed modeling translating the models into programming code. Class diagrams can also be used for data modeling.

Fig 4.8 Class Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements defined by any operating system or software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware. The minimal hardware requirements are as follows,

- Processor : Pentium IV
- RAM : 8 GB
- Processor : 2.4 GHz
- Main Memory : 8GB RAM
- Hard Disk Drive : 1tb
- Keyboard : 104 Keys

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software requirements deals with defining resource requirements and prerequisites that needs to be installed on a computer to provide functioning of an application. The minimal software requirements are as follows,

- Front end : python
- Dataset : csv
- IDE : anaconda
- Operating System : Windows 10

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 Python Language

Python is an object-oriented programming language created by Guido Rossum in 1989. It is ideally designed for rapid prototyping of complex applications. It has interfaces to many OS system calls and libraries and is extensible to C or C++. Many large companies use the Python programming language include NASA, Google, YouTube, BitTorrent, etc. Python programming is widely used in Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Generation, Neural Networks and other advanced fields of Computer Science. Python had deep focus on code readability & this class will teach you python from basics.

Python Programming Characteristics

- It provides rich data types and easier to read syntax than any other programming languages
- It is a platform independent scripted language with full access to operating system API's
- Compared to other programming languages, it allows more run-time flexibility
- It includes the basic text manipulation facilities of Perl and Awk
- A module in Python may have one or more classes and free functions
- Libraries in Python's are cross-platform compatible with Linux, Macintosh, and Windows
- For building large applications, Python can be compiled to byte-code
- Python supports functional and structured programming as well as OOP
- It supports interactive mode that allows interacting Testing and debugging of snippets of code
- In Python, since there is no compilation step, editing, debugging and testing is fast.

Applications of Python Programming

Web Applications

You can create scalable Web Apps using frameworks and CMS (Content Management System) that are built on Python. Some of the popular platforms for creating Web Apps are: Django, Flask, Pyramid, Plone, Django CMS. Sites like Mozilla, Reddit, Instagram and PBS are written in Python.

Scientific and Numeric Computing

There are numerous libraries available in Python for scientific and numeric computing. There are libraries like: SciPy and NumPy that are used in general purpose computing. And, there are specific libraries like: EarthPy for earth science, AstroPy for Astronomy and so on. Also, the language is heavily used in machine learning, data mining and deep learning.

Creating software Prototypes

Python is slow compared to compiled languages like C++ and Java. It might not be a good choice if resources are limited and efficiency is a must. However, Python is a great language for creating prototypes. For example: You can use Pygame (library for creating games) to create your game's prototype first. If you like the prototype, you can use language like C++ to create the actual game.

Good Language to Teach Programming

Python is used by many companies to teach programming to kids and newbies. It is a good language with a lot of features and capabilities. Yet, it's one of the easiest language to learn because of its simple easy-to-use syntax.

6.1.2 Opencv Package

Python is a general purpose programming language started by Guido van Rossum, which became very popular in short time mainly because of its simplicity and code readability. It enables the programmer to express his ideas in fewer lines of code without reducing any readability.

Compared to other languages like C/C++, Python is slower. But another important feature of Python is that it can be easily extended with C/C++. This feature helps us to write

computationally intensive codes in C/C++ and create a Python wrapper for it so that we can use these wrappers as Python modules. This gives us two advantages: first, our code is as fast as original C/C++ code (since it is the actual C++ code working in background) and second, it is very easy to code in Python. This is how OpenCV-Python works, it is a Python wrapper around original C++ implementation.

And the support of Numpy makes the task more easier. Numpy is a highly optimized library for numerical operations. It gives a MATLAB-style syntax. All the OpenCV array structures are converted to-and-from Numpy arrays. So whatever operations you can do in Numpy, you can combine it with OpenCV, which increases number of weapons in your arsenal. Besides that, several other libraries like SciPy, Matplotlib which supports Numpy can be used with this.

So OpenCV-Python is an appropriate tool for fast prototyping of computer vision problems.

6.1.3 FEATURES OF ANACONDA NAVIGATOR

Anaconda

Anaconda is a free and open source, easy to install distribution of Python and R programming languages. Anaconda provides a working environment which is used for scientific computing, data science, statistical analysis and machine learning.

The latest distribution of Anaconda is Anaconda 5.3 and is released in October, 2018. It has the conda package, environment manager and a collection of 1000+ open source packages long with free community support.

What is Anaconda Navigator?

Anaconda Navigator is a desktop graphical user interface (GUI) included in the Anaconda distribution. It allows us to launch applications provided in the Anaconda distribution and easily manage conda packages, environments and channels without the use of command-line commands. It is available for Windows, macOS and Linux.

Anaconda Navigator

Applications Provided In Anaconda Distribution

The Anaconda distribution comes with the following applications along with Anaconda Navigator.

1. JupyterLab
2. Jupyter Notebook
3. Qt Console
4. Spyder
5. Glueviz
6. Orange3
7. RStudio
8. Visual Studio Code

> JupyterLab: This is an extensible working environment for interactive and reproducible computing, based on the Jupyter Notebook and Architecture.

> Jupyter Notebook: This is a web-based, interactive computing notebook environment. We can edit and run human-readable docs while describing the data analysis.

> Qt Console: It is the PyQt GUI that supports inline figures, proper multiline editing with syntax highlighting, graphical calltips and more.

> Spyder: Spyder is a scientific Python Development Environment. It is a powerful Python IDE with advanced editing, interactive testing, debugging and introspection features.

> VS Code: It is a streamlined code editor with support for development operations like debugging, task running and version control.

> Glueviz: This is used for multidimensional data visualization across files. It explores relationships within and among related datasets.

> Orange 3: It is a component-based data mining framework. This can be used for data visualization and data analysis. The workflows in Orange 3 are very interactive and provide a large toolbox.

> Rstudio: It is a set of integrated tools designed to help you be more productive with R. It includes R essentials and notebooks.

New Features of Anaconda 5.3

Compiled with Latest Python release: Anaconda 5.3 is compiled with Python 3.7, taking advantage of Python's speed and feature improvements.

- **Better Reliability:** The reliability of Anaconda has been improved in the latest release by capturing and storing the package metadata for installed packages.

- **Enhanced CPU Performance:** The Intel Math Kernel Library 2019 for Deep Neural Networks(MKL 2019) has been introduced in Anaconda 5.3 distribution. Users deploying Tensorflow can make use of MKL 2019 for Deep Neural Networks. These Python binary packages are provided to achieve high CPU performance.

- **New packages are added:** There are over 230 packages which has been updated and added in the new release.

- **Work in Progress:** There is a casting bug in Numpy with Python 3.7 but the team is currently working on patching it until Numpy is updated.

6.2. LIST OF MODULES:

1. Data Capturing
2. Data Pre-Processing
3. Background Subtraction
4. Morphological Filtering
5. Feature Extraction

6.3 MODULES DESCRIPTION:

1. Data Capturing

The initial move is to capture the image from camera and to define a region of Interest in the frame, it is important as the image can contain a lot of variables and these variables can result in unwanted results and the data that needs to be processed is reduced to a large extent. To capture the image a web-camera is used that continuously captures frames and is used to get the raw data for processing. The input picture we have here is uint8. The Procured image is RGB and must be processed before i.e. pre-processed before the components are separated and acknowledgement is made.

2. Data Pre-Processing:

Pre-processing method can be completed 2-steps process:

- Segmentation
- Morphological filtering

First Process is the Segmentation process. It is done to change over grey-scale picture into the binary picture so we can have just two Area of Interest in picture. That is, one will be hand and another one is background. Algorithm can be Haar Cascade used for this process

and gray scale picture are converted into binary picture having area of interest as the hand and the background.

There are two main approaches to segmentation:

1. Pixel-based or local methods having: -

- a) Edge detection
- b) Boundary detection.

2. Region-based approach: -

- a) The region merging
- b) The region splitting
- c) Thresholding method

Thresholding techniques is employed in partitioning the image pixel histogram by using a single threshold technique. We in this project have used otsu's thresholding technique. HaarCascade thresholding is used to automatically perform clusterbased thresholding. The method assumes there are two classes of pixels following bi modal histogram and then it calculates optimum threshold separating the two classes

3. BACKGROUND SUBTRACTION

Background subtraction (BS) is a common and widely used technique for generating a foreground mask (namely, a binary image containing the pixels belonging to moving objects in the scene) by using static cameras.

As the name suggests, BS calculates the foreground mask performing a subtraction between the current frame and a background model, containing the static part of the scene or, more in general, everything that can be considered as background given the characteristics of the observed scene.

Background modeling consists of two main steps:

Background Initialization;

Background Update.

In the first step, an initial model of the background is computed, while in the second step that model is updated in order to adapt to possible changes in the scene.

4.MORPHOLOGICAL FILTERING:

After thresholding we have to make sure that there will be no noise is present in image, so we are using morphological filtering Techniques, These Techniques are divided in 3 parts.

- a. Dilation
- b. Erosion
- c. Opening and
- d. Closing

If the division is not continuous, then there may have some '_1s' in the background which is called as background noise, Also, there is a possibility that system generated an error in recognizing gesture this may be termed as gesture noise. If we want flawless contour detection of a gesture, then abovementioned errors should be nullified. A morphological separating (filtering) approach is employed utilizing grouping of dilation (enlargement) and erosion (disintegration) to accomplish a smooth, shut, and finish the contours of a hand motion.

5. Features Extraction

Pre-prepared or preprocessed picture is accessible to be utilized and different highlights of the resultant picture are removed. Following are the features that can be extracted:

- Finding Contours
- Finding and correcting convex hull
- Action

1. **Contours:** It implies the direction of hand i.e. regardless of whether the hand is on a horizontal plane or vertically set. Initially, we try to find the orientation by length to width ratio with a presumption that if the hand is vertical ten length of the box bounding them will be more than the width of the same box and, if hand is horizontally placed then width

of bounding box is larger than width of the box binding the hand will be more than that of the length of the box.

2. Finding and correcting convex hulls: A hand posture is recognized by its own orientation and by the fact that how many fingers are shown. For getting the aggregate of how many fingers are shown in hand motions that we have to process just area of the finger of the hand that we have in past advance by figuring out and analyzing the centroid.

3. Action:

Number of fingers trips detected	Operation performed
Two	Volume increase
Three	Forward
Four	Backward
Five	Volume decrease

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 General

In a generalized way, we can say that the system testing is a type of testing in which the main aim is to make sure that system performs efficiently and seamlessly. The process of testing is applied to a program with the main aim to discover an unprecedented error, an error which otherwise could have damaged the future of the software. Test cases which brings up a high possibility of discovering and error is considered successful. This successful test helps to answer the still unknown errors.

TEST CASE

Testing, as already explained earlier, is the process of discovering all possible weak-points in the finalized software product. Testing helps to counter the working of sub-assemblies, components, assembly and the complete result. The software is taken through different exercises with the main aim of making sure that software meets the business requirement and user-expectations and doesn't fails abruptly. Several types of tests are used today. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement.

Testing Techniques

A test plan is a document which describes approach, its scope, its resources and the schedule of aimed testing exercises. It helps to identify almost other test item, the features which are to be tested, its tasks, how will everyone do each task, how much the tester is independent, the environment in which the test is taking place, its technique of design plus the both the end criteria which is used, also rational of choice of theirs, and whatever kind of risk which requires emergency planning. It can be also referred to as the record of the process of test planning. Test plans are usually prepared with signification input from test engineers.

7.2 TYPES OF TESTING

7.2.1 UNIT TESTING

In unit testing, the design of the test cases is involved that helps in the validation of the internal program logic. The validation of all the decision branches and internal code takes place. After the individual unit is completed it takes place. Plus it is taken into account after the individual unit is completed before integration. The unit test thus performs the basic level test at its component stage and test the particular business process, system configurations etc. The unit test ensures that the particular unique path of the process gets performed precisely to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs with the results which are expected.

7.2.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

These tests are designed to test the integrated software items to determine whether if they really execute as a single program or application. The testing is event driven and thus is concerned with the basic outcome of field. The Integration tests demonstrate that the components were individually satisfaction, as already represented by successful unit testing, the components are apt and fine. This type of testing is specially aimed to expose the issues that come-up by the components combination.

7.2.3 FUNCTIONAL TESTING

The functional tests help in providing the systematic representation that functions tested are available and specified by technical requirement, documentation of the system and the user manual.

7.2.4 SYSTEM TESTING

System testing, as the name suggests, is the type of testing in which ensure that the software system meet the business requirements and aim. Testing of the configuration is taken place here to ensure predictable result and thus analysis of it. System testing is relied on the description of process and its flow, stressing on pre driven process and the points of integration.

7.2.5 WHITE BOX TESTING

The white box testing is the type of testing in which the internal components of the system software is open and can be processed by the tester. It is therefore a complex type of testing process. All the data structure, components etc. are tested by the tester himself to find out a possible bug or error. It is used in situation in which the black box is incapable of finding out a bug. It is a complex type of testing which takes more time to get applied.

7.2.6 BLACK BOX TESTING

The black box testing is the type of testing in which the internal components of the software is hidden and only the input and output of the system is the key for the tester to find out a bug. It is therefore a simple type of testing. A programmer with basic knowledge can also process this type of testing. It is less time consuming as compared to the white box testing. It is very successful for software which are less complex are straight-forward in nature. It is also less costly than white box testing.

7.2.7 ACCEPTANCE TESTING

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

7.2.8 ALPHA TESTING

Alpha testing is performed at the developer's site by the customer in a closed environment. This is done after the system testing. Alpha testing is one of the most common software testing strategies used in software development. It's specially used by product development organizations. Alpha testing is typically performed by a group that is independent of the design team, but still within the company, e.g. in-house software test engineers, or software QA engineers. Alpha testing is final testing before the software is released to the general public.

7.2.9 BETA TESTING

It is also known as field testing. It takes place at customer's sites. It sends the system to users who install it and use it under real-world working conditions. A beta test is the second phase of software testing in which a sampling of the intended audience tries the product out.

7.2.10 SECURITY TESTING

Security testing is basically a type of software testing that's done to check whether the application or the product is secured or not. It checks to see if the application is vulnerable to attacks, if anyone hack the system or login to the application without any authorization. It is a type of non-functional testing. It is a process to determine that an information system protects data and maintains functionality as intended. The security testing is performed to check whether there is any information leakage in the sense by encrypting the application or using wide range of software's and hardware's and firewall etc.

7.3 TEST CASE RESULTS

Test	Requirements	Test data	Expected data	Actual data	Pass or Fail
Volume Up	Youtube	Five Fingers	Volume increase	Increase in volume	Pass
Volume down	Youtube	Two Fingers	Volume decrease	Decrease in Volume	Pass
Forward	Youtube	Three Fingers	Forward in video	Video forward	Pass
Backward	Youtube	Four Fingers	Reverse in video	Video reverse	Pass
Next slide	Microsoft presentation	Three Fingers	Slide changes	Moves to next slide	Pass
Previous slide	Microsoft presentation	Four Fingers	Slide changes	Moves to previous slide	Pass

Table 7.3 Test Case Results

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A significant hand gesture recognition for human-computer interaction. In this work, we present a novel real-time method for hand gesture recognition, which uses machine learning techniques and inputs from computer webcam. Our proposed device will be a real time system along with easy to use interface which will be proved in terms of security of people as well as their valuable things/objects. Moreover, our methodology shows better performance than a state-of-art method on another data set of hand gestures.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

9.1 CONCLUSION

The vision based cursor control using hand gesture system was developed in the python language, using the OpenCV library. The system was able to control the movement of a Cursor by tracking the users hand. Cursor functions were performed by using different hand gestures. The system has the potential of being a viable replacement for the computer mouse, however due to the constraints encountered; it cannot completely replace the computer mouse.

9.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

We will improve the performance of the software especially hand tracking in the near future. In future, we will implement this process to control the system without the usage of keyboard and mouse completely. To design a hardware implementation for the same in order to improve accuracy and increase the functionality to various domains such as a gaming controller or as a general purpose computer controller. Other advanced implementation include the hand gesture recognition.

APPENDICES

A.SAMPLE CODE

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
import copy
import math
import pyautogui as pa

cap_region_x_begin=0.5 # start point/total width
cap_region_y_end=0.8 # start point/total width
threshold = 60 # BINARY thresholdq
blurValue = 41 # GaussianBlur parameter
bgSubThreshold = 50
learningRate = 0

# variables
isBgCaptured = 0 # bool, whether the background captured
triggerSwitch = False # if true, keyborad simulator works

def printThreshold(thr):
    print("! Changed threshold to "+str(thr))

def removeBG(frame):
    fgmask = bgModel.apply(frame,learningRate=learningRate)
    # kernel = cv2.getStructuringElement(cv2.MORPH_ELLIPSE, (3, 3))
    # res = cv2.morphologyEx(fgmask, cv2.MORPH_OPEN, kernel)

    kernel = np.ones((3, 3), np.uint8)
    fgmask = cv2.erode(fgmask, kernel, iterations=1)
    res = cv2.bitwise_and(frame, frame, mask=fgmask)
    return res

def calculateFingers(res,drawing): # -> finished bool, cnt: finger count
    # convexity defect
    hull = cv2.convexHull(res, returnPoints=False)
    if len(hull) > 3:
        defects = cv2.convexityDefects(res, hull)
```

```

if type(defects) != type(None): # avoid crashing. (BUG not found)

    cnt = 0
    for i in range(defects.shape[0]): # calculate the angle
        s, e, f, d = defects[i][0]
        start = tuple(res[s][0])
        end = tuple(res[e][0])
        far = tuple(res[f][0])
        a = math.sqrt((end[0] - start[0]) ** 2 + (end[1] - start[1]) ** 2)
        b = math.sqrt((far[0] - start[0]) ** 2 + (far[1] - start[1]) ** 2)
        c = math.sqrt((end[0] - far[0]) ** 2 + (end[1] - far[1]) ** 2)
        angle = math.acos((b ** 2 + c ** 2 - a ** 2) / (2 * b * c)) # cosine
theorem
        if angle <= math.pi / 2: # angle less than 90 degree, treat as fingers
            cnt += 1
            cv2.circle(drawing, far, 8, [211, 84, 0], -1)
    return True, cnt
return False, 0

```

Camera

```

camera = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
camera.set(10,200)
cv2.namedWindow('trackbar')
cv2.createTrackbar('trh1', 'trackbar', threshold, 100, printThreshold)
ee=0
cc=0
dd=0
ff=0
while camera.isOpened():
    ret, frame = camera.read()
    threshold = cv2.getTrackbarPos('trh1', 'trackbar')
    frame = cv2.bilateralFilter(frame, 5, 50, 100) # smoothing filter
    frame = cv2.flip(frame, 1) # flip the frame horizontally
    cv2.rectangle(frame, (int(cap_region_x_begin * frame.shape[1]), 0),
                  (frame.shape[1], int(cap_region_y_end * frame.shape[0])), (255, 0,
0), 2)
    cv2.imshow('original', frame)

# Main operation
if isBgCaptured == 1: # this part wont run until background captured
    img = removeBG(frame)
    img = img[0:int(cap_region_y_end * frame.shape[0]),

```

```

int(cap_region_x_begin * frame.shape[1]):frame.shape[1]] #
clip the ROI
cv2.imshow('mask', img)

# convert the image into binary image
gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
blur = cv2.GaussianBlur(gray, (blurValue, blurValue), 0)
cv2.imshow('blur', blur)
ret, thresh = cv2.threshold(blur, threshold, 255, cv2.THRESH_BINARY)
cv2.imshow('ori', thresh)

# get the coutours
thresh1 = copy.deepcopy(thresh)
_,contours, hierarchy = cv2.findContours(thresh1, cv2.RETR_TREE,
cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)
length = len(contours)
maxArea = -1
if length > 0:
    for i in range(length): # find the biggest contour (according to area)
        temp = contours[i]
        area = cv2.contourArea(temp)
        if area > maxArea:
            maxArea = area
            ci = i

res = contours[ci]
hull = cv2.convexHull(res)
drawing = np.zeros(img.shape, np.uint8)
cv2.drawContours(drawing, [res], 0, (0, 255, 0), 2)
cv2.drawContours(drawing, [hull], 0, (0, 0, 255), 3)

isFinishCal,cnt = calculateFingers(res,drawing)

if triggerSwitch is True:
    if isFinishCal is True and cnt <= 4:
        print (cnt)
        if cnt==3:
            cc+=1
            if cc==20:
                pa.press("left")
                print("hii")
                cc=0

```

```

        else:
            pass

    elif cnt==4:
        dd+=1
        if dd==15:
            pa.press("up")
            dd=0
        else:
            pass
    elif cnt==1:
        ee+=1
        if ee==10:
            pa.press("down")
            ee=0
        else:
            pass
    elif cnt==2:
        ff+=1
        if ff==5:
            pa.press("right")
            ff=0
        else:
            pass
    else:
        pass

    #app('System Events').keystroke(' ') # simulate pressing blank
space

```

```

cv2.imshow('output', drawing)

```

```

# Keyboard OP

```

```

k = cv2.waitKey(10)

```

```

if k == 27: # press ESC to exit

```

```

    camera.release()

```

```

    cv2.destroyAllWindows()

```

```

    break

```

```

elif k == ord('b'): # press 'b' to capture the background

```

```

    bgModel = cv2.createBackgroundSubtractorMOG2(0, bgSubThreshold)

```

```

    isBgCaptured = 1

```

```

    print( '!!!Background Captured!!!')

```

```

elif k == ord('r'): # press 'r' to reset the background

```

```
bgModel = None
triggerSwitch = False
isBgCaptured = 0
print ('!!!Reset BackGround!!!')
elif k == ord('n'):
    triggerSwitch = True
    print ('!!!Trigger On!!!')
```

B. SCREENSHOTS

Get Convex Points
in contour

Get points furthest away
from each convex vertex
(convexity defects)

Filter out
convexity defects
not relevant

Detects 5 fingertips

Detects 4 fingertips

Detects 3 fingertips

Detects 2 fingertips

Original image from Background Substraction

Blur image from Background Substraction

Volume Increase

Volume Decrease

Forward

Backward

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